

on the 20th day (see table).

Even low lime levels of 1,250 kg/ha inhibited BGA growth significantly; BGA inhibition increased as lime increased.

Contrary to general belief, lime application did not control GA in the BGA multiplication units (see table). ■

Response of rice varieties to zinc treatment in farmers' fields at DND irrigation project, BWDB, Bangladesh

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Zinc deficiency in Bangladesh rice fields seems to be more acute in the irrigated areas (where the lands are kept wet for longer periods than in other areas) and in calcareous soils. In 1979, zinc deficiency was suspected in the BRR1-BWDB collaborative cropping systems research site at Shimrail in the DND irrigation project of the BWDB. A superimposed zinc treatment used 2% ZnO solution as seedling dip for 4 rice varieties grown by farmers in the area. Crop-cuts were made and grain yields adjusted at 14% moisture to determine the effect of zinc treatment on grain yield. IR8 responded tremendously to zinc treatment, yielding an extra 1.1 t/ha over the control (see table). The response of the local varieties to zinc application, in terms of increased grain yield, was only 0.1 t/ha. Studies on the problem are being continued. ■

Effect of dipping roots of rice seedlings in 2% ZnO on yield at Dacca-Narayanganj-Demra irrigation project, BWDB. 1979 transplanted aman season, Bangladesh.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	With zinc	Without zinc	Difference
IR8 ^a	3.8	2.7	1.1
Pajam ^b	3.0	2.9	0.1
Nizersail ^b	3.4	3.3	0.1
Pagu ^c	3.2	3.1	0.1

^aAv of trials in 3 plots. ^bAv of trials in 2 plots.

^c Trial in 1 plot.

Role of direct-seeded rice in Sudan Gezira crop rotation

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Rice is cultivated in the Sudan Gezira as an irrigated, direct-seeded crop in a four-course rotation (cotton-wheat-groundnuts-fallow). Although the role of rice in this rotation has not been investigated in depth, the current practice is to grow rice instead of groundnuts or fallow. Apparently, this practice is not very appropriate because numerous studies carried out at GRS have shown that the soil nitrogen content is usually too low to sustain a rice crop under these conditions, considering the high nitrogen losses in this environment. Therefore, relatively high rates of nitrogen fertilizers are required to attain high rice yields; 140 kg N/ha is considered as the optimum level for rice. Furthermore, there are some indications that a preceding crop does not influence rice performance solely through its effects on soil nitrogen content but, even more important, through effects on soil physical and chemical characteristics.

IR2053-206-1-3-6 was grown at seven

nitrogen levels after phillipesara, sesame, and fallow at GRS for three seasons, 1977-79. The nitrogen treatments were arranged in four replications in a randomized complete block design.

Rice yields increased progressively and significantly ($P = 0.001$) with increased nitrogen levels up to 160 kg N/ha. Beyond that level, yield increases were nonsignificant. But rice yield potentials differed greatly: 7.0 t/ha after sesame, 6.1 t/ha after phillipesara, and 5.0 t/ha after fallow. The increases in grain yield with an increase in applied nitrogen were generally similar in each rotation. The beneficial effects of sesame as an excellent precursor to other crops in the Sudan's central rain lands and of phillipesara in the Gezira were well established. From extrapolation of the results (see figure), it appears that only phillipesara increased soil nitrogen content. But because the application of higher nitrogen levels did not compensate for the differences in observed yield potentials, a preceding crop's influence on rice may be due to other physical or chemical soil properties. Integration of rice in a suitable rotation currently dominated by other crops is an important consideration. ■

Response of IR2053-206-1-3-6 grown as irrigated direct-seeded crop after phillipesara, sesame, and fallow at different nitrogen levels. Gezira Research Station, Sudan, 1977-79.